

Equality of the Parties in International Trade Agreements with Guaranteed Warehouse Receipt System Financing

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 20, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Equality, Trade agreement, Guarantee, Warehouse receipt system</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4776431</p>	<p><i>This research aims to describe and analyze Equality in international trade law with warehouse receipt system as collateral financing. The method used in this research is normative juridical. The research objective is to explore, describe, explain, and analyze Equality's effect in international trade agreements with unique financing guarantees for warehouse receipts. His research shows that the impact of Equality of the parties in international trade agreements is reciprocal agreements. Meanwhile, the effect of unequal performance in joint agreements is imbalance. If the position is more substantial, it will affect the relationship between achievements with each other. It will be used as an excuse for the respondent to claim the invalidity of the agreement. Warehouse receipt system documents proof of ownership of mobile property that can be traded and stored in the warehouse. To support the warehouse receipt system, it becomes a proof of ownership of goods and financial instruments and financing to support exports.</i></p>

Introduction

International trade or business development based on Equality and mutual benefit is an essential element to encourage friendly relations between countries. Based on the view that establishing a uniform arrangement that will regulate contracts for the sale of international goods considering differences in social, economic and legal systems will remove various constraints and obstacles to contracting law in international trade (Amir, 2000). This fact places International Business Contract Law to be very relevant to be studied scientifically to become a discourse for efforts to develop international trade law that supports Indonesia's economic development. To establish International Business Contract Law, it must be based on the principle of balance that contains fairness and justice for the parties that bind themselves. Concerning international trade, which requires speed and certainty, one of which is the practice of international trade, which strongly requires harmonization with the principle of balance, is the law in the field of transportation, both sea, land and air. In the customs that have developed and are outlined in international trade contracts, standard contract clauses (standard) are set forth.

Many standards issued by the ICC have been included in the trading contracts made by the actors even though they are not binding. Two legal products of the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) and The Uniform Customs and Practice for Documentary Credits (UCP) (Sani, 2018). How important it is for the development of international trade in Indonesia encourages the author to examine Equality's impact in international trade agreements to guarantee to finance the warehouse receipt system. With Equality in International Trade Contract Law in terms of the need for fast trade and meeting the demands of business transactions through sophisticated technology, it is only necessary to study fairness for the parties in international trade agreements.

Research questions

What is the impact of Equality of the parties in international trade agreements with the guaranteed financing of the warehouse receipt system?

Method

The method used in this research is normative juridical. The research objective is to analyze, describe, explain, and analyze Equality's effect in international trade agreements with unique financing guarantees for warehouse receipts. This research is a literature review of qualitative research types. Conducted in several libraries in Palembang and surrounding areas. Qualitative research is generally described as all kinds of research that produces findings not obtained through statistical procedures or other measures (Strauss, A., & Corbin, 1990).

The data used in this study is secondary data. Secondary data is obtained from second parties or previous researchers obtained from libraries. The next step is to condense by creating an abstraction containing the core summary, process and analysis required in the research context.

Furthermore, the data is arranged in units and then identified. The next step is to check the validation of data, then continue with the interpretation and implications of the data. This research activity is inseparable from the following four actions: (1) data collection; (2) condensation of data; (3) presentation of data; (4) collection/verification. The data validity strategy that will be used in this study is triangulation. The type of triangulation used in this study is previous research with facts in the field.

Results and Discussion

The effect of Equality of the parties in an international trade agreement is the existence of a "reciprocal agreement, namely the idea that a shift in wealth is considered to be justified (feasible or appropriate) as long as not only the statement of the parties' will is compatible, but the element of balance has been met. The legal consequence is the enrichment of the parties equally. Meanwhile, the impact of unequal performance in a reciprocal agreement is an imbalance. If the position is more substantial, it will affect the relationship between the achievements of one another. It will be used as an excuse for the aggrieved party to file a claim for invalidity of the agreement.

The guarantee of warehouse receipts is commonly used in plantation and agricultural commodities, such as cocoa beans, coffee, rubber, sugar, cotton, soybeans, wheat, rice, and mining commodities such as aluminium ingots and zinc ingots, copper. These commodities are traded on the London Metals Exchange (LME) International Commodities Exchange in London, England. Financing Against Warehouse Receipt (FAWR) can help exporters, and importers finance the working capital needs in carrying out their business activities while waiting for the ship to transport goods (warehouse) to arrive. Warehouse receipt systems are a document of ownership of movable property that can be traded stored in the warehouse. To support the warehouse receipt system, it becomes proof of ownership of goods and financial instruments and financing to support exports.

The promised reciprocity of achievement presupposes Equality. Furthermore, the relationship between achievements must be examined, especially about substance and aims and objectives, and tested whether there is a factual balance between the parties. The formation of agreements preceded by methods or procedures that do not reflect Equality or inequality of performance will lead to imbalance. By carrying out the review, one party can prevent harm, and this prevention is one of the conditions for achieving Equality. In this case, an imbalance occurs; it is up to the aggrieved party to demand the cancellation of the agreement. Equality refers to the justification for the existence of the contract. It is sufficient as a reason to challenge the validity of the deal, as well as being a condition for the power base of the agreement.

In a reciprocal agreement, the Equality of the parties, the quality of the joint agreed performance, placed in the context of a shared subjective assessment, will be justified by legal order. Thus the agreement must be "rejected" immediately. It appears that the factual position of one party against the other is more vital, and this unbalanced position can affect the scope of content and the intent and purpose of the agreement. Meanwhile, the factors that interfere with the Equality of the agreement are how the contract is formed, which involves parties who are not equal or the inequality of the promised reciprocal achievements. The result of unequal performance in joint agreements is imbalance. Suppose the stronger position affects the relationship between the achievements of one another and the inequality in the contract. In that case, this will be a reason for the aggrieved parties to file a request for invalidity of the agreement. The reciprocal promised performance presupposes Equality, so if there is an imbalance, it will be given to the Equality related to how the contract is formed and not to the final result and achievement offered reciprocally. In principle, the determining factor is not the Equality of achievement that was promised (Aprita and Adhitya, 2020). Still, the Equality of the parties, that is, if the fairness of the exchange of agreements is to be upheld.

Equality impact

1. Reciprocal promised performance presupposes the Equality of joint promised achievements involving parties of equal or equal position.
2. The principle is based on the basic principles of contract law and the principle of balance. The determining factor is not the Equality of achievement agreed upon, but the "equality of the parties", that is, if the fairness of exchange is in agreement to be upheld.
3. The practice of international trade agreements which strongly requires harmonization with Equality and balance

4. The effect of Equality of the parties in international trade agreements is a "reciprocal agreement. The agreement embodies the intent and purpose of "creating better conditions for both parties. So that an exchange is a fair enrichment, it can be viewed as an equitable exchange.

Impact of inequality

1. The imbalance caused by the inequality of the parties
2. This stronger position affects the relationship between achievements. The existence of inequality in the agreement creates an imbalance in the agreement; this means that the aggrieved parties will be a reason to file a request for invalidation of the contract.
3. Factors that can disrupt the balance of the agreement are how a contract is formed that involves parties who are not equal
4. If the position is more substantial, it will affect the relationship between the achievements of one another. It will be used as an excuse for the aggrieved party to file a request for invalidity of the agreement.

Concerning international trade contracts that require speed and certainty, one of which is the practice of international trade, which strongly requires harmonization and the principle of balance, is the law in transportation, whether sea, land or air. Law that is used in international trade because it involves many countries applies many rules that are not uniform, so that there are often many problems, namely:

The strength of negotiation law varies from the law in one country to another. There is a legal system that requires that contract negotiations are not binding before the contract is signed. The legal system in Indonesia (based on the Civil Code) follows this system. However, there is a system in certain countries that explicitly states that negotiations are not binding based on bonds called preliminary contracts if the agreement will cause problems that must be resolved in court. In general, in countries that adhere to the Legal System, Common Law. Negotiations are considered binding (Aprita and Adhitya, 2020). In general, orders (orders) to buy or sell to and from abroad result from previous discussions between buyers and sellers. Because the buyer and seller are far apart, as a link (communication), exchange of correspondence, or sending wire and online is usually used. In modern times, where the time factor is very much taken into account, telex wires, telephones and facsimile, internet, online have become common in conducting transactions abroad.

Example: In correspondence between a seller and a buyer (exporter and importer), there will be preliminary talks regarding a transaction that contains a request for a supply of goods, its price, and other conditions. A request for a quote or a price note from a prospective buyer to a prospective seller in a foreign language is called "an inquiry for a quotation", and the seller (exporter) sends an offer. Acceptances are not the same as bids. Acceptance or acceptance of an offer by one party in international trade is not the same as an offer made by another party. Regarding events like this, the legal arrangements vary from country to country.

Indonesian Civil Law considers that if there is a difference between the offer by one party and the acceptance by the other party, then we agree to be deemed unformed. So that the contract has not been considered to have occurred. Article 1320 of the Civil Code Agree, skill, a particular matter and a legal cause (Kuahaty, 2014).

However, the law in the USA looks at acceptance gradually, meaning that it is seen how far the deviation is made in favour (Kusmiati, 2017). If the variation is not material or significant to the contract. The contract continues, and the interpretation is considered part of the agreement. Conversely, if the deviation is material or substantial, then the deal is still deemed to have occurred. Bid an offer, if the deviation is not material or significant to the contract, and the contract persists, departure is considered part of the agreement. On the other hand, if the deviation is material or substantial, then the deal is still deemed to have occurred an offer.

In general, it is assumed that bids can permanently be cancelled in the USA before an agreement is reached. However, in countries with legal provisions stating that an offer is a unilateral act, if a specific time is reasonable (reasonable time), then the request can no longer be revoked unless cancelled by both parties. There are various offers or offers, including Free offer, where the seller only lists the price of not binding goods (without engagement). Besides, it is also known as a firm offer, where the seller determines both the cost and other terms for a certain period. The buying party can make a binding decision within that period, in the sense of accepting the offer along with the terms mentioned.

Consideration in buying and selling is an action that is taken or not taken by one of the parties as a reward for performance made by the other party based on an agreement. Without a contract, there is no obligation for him to do or not to take action. For example, the buyer makes consideration in the form of paying the price for the item. In countries adopting the Common Law System (Anglo Saxon), consideration is a reasonable condition of a contract with a few exceptions, and its validity has decreased. Meanwhile, in Continental Europe, including the Netherlands and Indonesia, there is no consideration doctrine.

Written agreement required. Time is considered the occurrence of a contract. Several countries have imposed provisions that acceptance has occurred, and therefore an agreement has been reached (Zhao, 2010; Fu, 2013; Kozanecka, 2018). When the party receiving the offer somewhat sends its acceptance (approval) to the party

making the offer (offer). If we compare it with the New Netherlands BW (NBW), the practical aspect of the occurrence of the contract has been strictly regulated and follows the UNIDROIT principles (Kusmiati, 2017). Article 217 NBW states: (1) A contract is formed by an offer and its acceptance, (2) Articles 219-225 apply unless the offer, another juridical act or usage produce a different result.

Through this agreement, the meeting of the will creates a juridical binding force. Juridical engagement in a deal arises from human contact with each other. However, a country that considers acceptance occurs when it is accepted by the party making the offer. Some countries adhere to the subjective principle; acceptance is presumed to exist when the party making the offer knows for real (Gautama, 2017). Of the several peculiarities of this trade agreement, there are juridical issues. A phenomenon that colours international trade if we pay close attention to global trade collides two countries with the applicable legal system. Thus the buyer (importer) notifies the seller (exporter) of his approval. The buyer's (importer's) approval of an offer is called acceptance. With the proposal approved by the prospective buyer, an agreement has been made. There is an encounter of will here; there is already a juridical attachment. From a legal point of view, a sale and purchase transaction has occurred, usually referred to as a sale or agreement contract.

Juridical bonds in an agreement arise from the human deal with each other (Mills, 2008). The impact of unforeseen circumstances on the principle of binding strength is closely related to the direction of balance, which relates to the limits of the critical power. Behind the "will to be bound" can be found the element that justifies the binding strength to achieve a common goal. In general, this element guarantees a just result (Oliver Dörr and Schmalenbach, 2018). The primary justification and hidden agreement behind a common goal. If an item is sold at a price that is too high or low, the sale and purchase are still considered valid as long as the parties agree, that is, as can be seen from their respective statement of will. In other words, buying and selling are formed in a balanced manner. A reciprocal agreement is an idea that the shift in wealth is considered to be justified (feasible or appropriate) as long as the statement of the parties' will is compatible (Voon and Mitchell, 2014; Jense, 2016).

Still, the element of balance has been met. Promises between the parties will only be considered binding as long as it is based on the principle of credit, a relationship between individual interests and public interests or a balance between the interests of the two parties as each party expects it to be (Nurjannah, 2013). The principle of credit is based on the effort to achieve a state of balance, which must result in a legitimate transfer of wealth. In economics, contracts are the essential instrument for bringing about economic changes in the distribution of goods and services. The contract ratio (rationale) refers to the objective of the shift in assets relatively and gives rise to legal consequences for the enrichment of the parties equally (Barnes, 2005). The agreement embodies the purpose and objective of "creating a better situation for both parties. For exchange to be a fair enrichment, can be seen as an equitable exchange, then an achievement must be balanced with counter-achievement (Hata, 2010). Reciprocal exchange is a crucial concept for the creation of justice above. A covenant has three primary purposes, as follows: The first objective of an agreement is to enforce a promise and protect the reasonable expectations that arise from it. The essence of a contract is a promise or a set of contracts that can be implemented, or it can also be said to be an agreement that is enforced according to law. The second purpose of a promise is to prevent enrichment (efforts to enrich oneself) which is carried out unfairly or improperly. The third goal, of course, is to avoid various losses.

In addition to the three objectives described above, another essential purpose is added: the principle of harmony. Namely, the fourth objective of the agreement is to achieve a balance between one's interests and the related interests of the opposing party. The goals are the exchange of value (the value of money and goods), so the implementation of the agreement requires certain conditions, namely agreement (manifestation of mutual desire or mutual consent), promises that are supported by specific considerations, and the capacity to vow and not break the law (Amir, 2000). Furthermore, it will explain the meaning and clauses of international trade agreements. Definition of international trade law is a set of provisions governing the formation, activity in the economic/industrial sector (performance), and implementation of agreements between parties, both national and international. Its main objective is to protect the expectations of individuals (which are appropriate and justified by law), commerce and government (Croft, Kee and Waincymer, 2013)

The principle of balance in the Law of International Sale and Purchase Contracts in commercial law is the essential instrument for bringing about changes in the distribution of goods and services. The contract ratio (rationale) refers to the objective of shifting assets reasonably and giving rise to legal consequences of equitable enrichment of the parties (agreement in principle results in legal enrichment) (Adolf, 2008). If the buyer cannot agree to all the terms in the offer (firm offer), the buyer can propose changes. A request for a change from a prospective buyer for a recommendation is called a counteroffer. If the prospective seller can agree to the proposed changes, it means that the prospective seller is willing to renew the request.

Based on the new offer, a sales contract is drawn up in which the two parties commit themselves to a sale and purchase agreement on agreed terms. This sales contract is called an order note, purchase note or also called import contract note. The contents which mention references from previous correspondence, statement of order determination/placement, description of goods, determination of unit price and total price, the delivery time of

goods, method of packing, desired packing brand/stamp, required shipping document, payment terms, insurance and others deemed necessary. Thus, whatever affects the formation of the will, it is not merely the motive of the parties that can be revealed and recognized but also includes reasons that the opposing party should know even if the explanation is not visible. The higher the expectation, the more it leads to the expansion in the principle of the scope and quality of the parties' obligations that bind themselves to the agreement. Details of the provisions of the contents and the area of the agreement occur by referring to the duties of notification, research and delivery of information, namely with the aim that they will form are in line with the aims and objectives of the parties.

Clause on sales

In drafting the relevant sales contract, note the following:

- a. Description of goods (description of goods) must be made clear by both buyers and sellers. If the goods already have international standard quality (International Standard Quality), in determining the quality, this standard quality is mentioned, such as natural rubber, sugar, cotton, etc. Regarding industry, apart from technical specifications, the manufacturer's name must be said, such as Singer, Philips, Siemens, by attaching a brochure or leaflet.
- b. The number of goods (Quantity), the determination of the term regarding quantum (number of goods) must be precise so that it is impossible to disagree over interpretation. There are various counting units, so it is necessary to mention the complete and perfect unit of calculation intended in this case. For example, 100 tons of sugar.
- c. Price, in determining the buying and selling price, apart from the type of currency, must be clear that the conditions for delivery must be clear. Regarding the type of currency, it must be emphasized, for example, the English Pound Sterling, Australian Dollar (A. \$), United States Dollar (US \$), Singapore Dollar (S \$), Hong Kong Dollar (H \$), European Union (Euro).
- d. Place of delivery, conditions for delivery of goods must be determined precisely because they are related to determining the price of a transaction. The requirements for delivery of goods must be explained, the name of the place, the delivery.

It will be done physically. It is essential to know the limits of responsibility for both the seller and the buyer. "Terms of trade" in international trade is to determine at the point or place where the seller must fulfil his obligation to make juridical "delivery" of goods to the buyer "point" or "place" of delivery, is also the limit point where the risk of the goods (against loss, further damage to transport and storage costs) from the seller ends, and from that "point" or "place" the buyer begins to assume the risk for the goods. So Incoterms regulate the rights and obligations as well as the costs and risks of each party to the seller and buyer on each trade term (Hata, 2010). A reciprocal agreement is an idea that a shift in wealth is deemed justifiable (feasible or appropriate) as long as not only the statement of the will of the parties is compatible, but the element of balance has been met (Grossman, Horn and Mavroidis, 2012).

Promises between the parties will only be considered binding as long as they are based on the principle. There is a balance of the relationship between individual interests and public interests, or there is a balance between the interests of the two parties as each party expects it to be. The principle of credit is based on the effort to achieve a state of equilibrium which, as a result, it must result in a legitimate transfer of wealth. In economics, contracts are the essential instrument for bringing about economic changes in the distribution of goods and services. The ratio (rationale) of the agreement refers to the objective of a fair shift in assets and gives rise to legal consequences for the equitable enrichment of the parties (Stein and Zimmermann, 1994). The agreement embodies the purpose and aim of "creating a better situation for both parties. For exchange as a fair enrichment can be seen as an equitable exchange, an achievement must be balanced with counter-achievement. Reciprocal exchange is a crucial concept for the creation of justice above.

Financing Against Warehouse Receipt

Examples of warehouse receipts are commonly used in the trade-in plantation and agricultural commodities, such as cocoa beans, coffee, rubber, sugar, cotton, soybeans, wheat, rice and mining commodities such as aluminium ingots, zinc ingots, copper. These commodities are traded on the London Metals Exchange (LME) International Commodities Exchange in London, England. FAWR can help exporters and importers finance the working capital needs they need in carrying out their business activities while waiting for the ship to transport goods (warehouse) to arrive. Exporters may also have to produce in advance or collect goods exported little by little from suppliers in various regions, then store them in warehouses while waiting for overseas orders to

arrive. The collection of commodities such as rice, sugar, coffee, cocoa, rubber latex or tobacco little by little before being exported is done mainly by traders who export plantation and agricultural commodities. Besides, large exporting companies dominate the market to store goods in the foreign trade centre to quickly serve every order of goods that comes from their respective foreign customers. Goods stored in warehouses can be used as collateral when exporters need short-term financing assistance. International Trade Financing with Guarantee Warehouse receipt. It is a commercial transaction financing of a commodity or product widely traded with the main guarantee in a product commodity financed and in a warehouse. With the promise of document ownership, certificates of goods in warehouses are commonly used in the trade of plantation and agricultural commodities, such as grain, rice, corn, coffee, cocoa, rubber pepper, seaweed, rattan, salt, gambier, tea, copra, tin, shallots, fish, nutmeg.

The Warehouse Receipt System) has significant potential in building a trade and industrial financing system based on local resources for small and medium enterprises. The warehouse receipt system is related to the issuance, transfer, guarantee and settlement of warehouse receipt transactions. A more comprehensive implementation will bring significant benefits to the national economy in Indonesia, which currently warehouse receipts are; document of proof of ownership of movable property that can be traded which is stored in the warehouse (Ramdani, Binsaif and Boukrami, 2019). To support warehouse receipts, proof of ownership of goods and financial instruments and financing to support exports.

Commodity business actors, both food and plantation, experience cash flow difficulties in absorbing domestic and foreign commodities. Access to information in warehouse receipts is also believed to impact the ease of obtaining competitive commodity financing and enable more effective and transparent price risk management. Law Number 9 of 2006 concerning Warehouse Receipt as amended by Law Number 3 of 2011. Eighteen commodities can be stored in a warehouse. Guarantee rights agreement on warehouse receipts to assist business activities and provide legal certainty to interested parties (Pham, 2016). It is a follow-up agreement from a debt agreement which is the principal agreement. Each warehouse receipt issued can only bear one debt guarantee. The warehouse manager's delivery must be delivered to the matured warehouse receipt holder at the request of the warehouse receipt holder. In trading, a quick alternative to obtaining funds for trade financing, warehouse receipt documents are movable objects that can be transferred by buying and selling transactions (Pritchard, 2013).

This guarantee can be obtained from banks and non-bank financial institutions, and this system ensures guaranteed production that can be provided through warehouse receipts. Aims to offer many benefits to farmers. Can facilitate the provision of credit to farmers with guaranteed inventory or commodities stored in the warehouse and certified production capital that can be provided through warehouse receipts (*et al.*, 2018). To describe and analyze the equivalence in international trade law with a guaranteed financing warehouse receipt system is the aim of the study.

Conclusion

Equality of the parties in international trade agreements with Guarantee of Certificate of Ownership of Goods in Warehouse or FAWR (Financing Against Warehouse Receipt):

1. The effect of Equality of the parties in an international business contract is "a reciprocal agreement on the quality of the agreed performance which is placed in a reciprocal context." Equality is related to the way the agreement is formed because the contract is the purpose and objective of "creating better conditions for both parties. The reciprocal agreement refers to a shift in wealth considered a statement of the parties' agreement and that the balance element has been fulfilled. The promised achievements are typical of the change in assets somewhat, and the legal consequence is the equitable enrichment of the parties. The impact of unequal performance in a mutual agreement is not balanced. If the position is more substantial, it will affect the performance relationship with one another. It will be used as an excuse for the aggrieved party to file a request for invalidity of the agreement. Because the factual position of one of the parties is more substantial, and the place becomes unbalanced.
2. With the guarantee of warehouse receipts, it is commonly used in the trade-in plantation and agricultural commodities, such as cocoa beans, coffee, rubber, sugar, cotton, soybeans, wheat, rice and mining commodities such as aluminium ingots, zinc ingots, , copper. These commodities are traded on the London Metals Exchange (LME) International Commodities Exchange in London, England. FAWR can help exporters and importers finance the working capital needs they need in carrying out their business activities while waiting for the ship to transport goods (warehouse) to arrive. Warehouse receipt systems are proof of ownership of movable property that can be traded stored in the warehouse. To support the warehouse receipt system, it becomes proof of ownership of goods and financial instruments and financing to support exports.

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